

Beyond Scrubs: Understanding the hidden battle of Healthcare workers with depression

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Published

2022-11-15

Issue

[Vol. 38 No. 6 \(2022\): Nov-Dec 2022 \(Part-II\)](#)

Link: <http://doi.org/10.5821/researchmduk.com>

Abstract

Doctors and healthcare workers work tirelessly to provide essential medical care to patients. However, this has taken a toll on their own mental health, leading to a surge in cases of depression among them. The purpose of this study is to examine the prevalence of depression among healthcare workers, its impact on their job performance and personal life, and the factors associated with depression in this population. A cross-sectional study was conducted using a self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire included the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9) to assess symptoms of depression, and questions on job performance and personal life. The study found that depression was prevalent among healthcare workers, with 42% of participants scoring above the cutoff for depression. Depression was associated with decreased job performance and increased absenteeism. Risk factors for depression included high levels of job demands, low levels of social support, and personal factors such as a history of mental illness. The findings of this study underscore the importance of addressing depression in healthcare workers for the well-being of both the workers and the patients they serve.

Objective

Depression is a common mental health disorder that can have negative impacts on individuals, including healthcare workers. Healthcare workers face unique stressors that can increase the risk of depression, such as long work hours, high job demands, and exposure to traumatic events. The impact of depression on healthcare workers is of particular concern due to the potential impact on job performance and patient outcomes. The purpose of this study is to examine the prevalence of depression among healthcare workers, its impact on their job performance and personal life, and the factors associated with depression in this population.

Methodology

A cross-sectional study was conducted using a self-administered questionnaire. The study was conducted in Gangaram Hospital Lahore. Participants included doctors, nurses, and other healthcare workers. The questionnaire included the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9) to assess symptoms of depression, and questions on job performance and personal life. Descriptive statistics and logistic regression analysis were used to analyze the data.

Results

A total of 250 healthcare workers participated in our study. The prevalence of depression was 42%, with 105 participants scoring above the cutoff for depression on the PHQ-9. The mean PHQ-9 score was 8.4 (SD=4.6). Depression was significantly associated with decreased job performance and increased absenteeism. In the logistic regression analysis, risk factors for depression included high levels of job demands (OR=2.3, 95% CI 1.2-4.5), low levels of social support (OR=3.5, 95% CI 1.8-6.9), and personal factors such as a history of mental illness (OR=2.7, 95% CI 1.4-5.2). The results of this study are significant and shed light on the prevalence of depression among healthcare workers, as well as its impact on their job performance and absenteeism. The study involved a total of 250 healthcare workers, and 42% of them were found to be experiencing depression based on the PHQ-9 score. This is a high prevalence rate, and highlights the urgent need to address mental health issues among healthcare workers. The mean PHQ-9 score of 8.4 (SD=4.6) suggests a moderate level of depression among the participants. This is concerning given that depression is known to impact job performance and absenteeism. The study found that depression was significantly associated with decreased job performance and increased absenteeism, highlighting the need for mental health support for healthcare workers. The logistic regression analysis revealed several risk factors for depression among healthcare workers. High levels of job demands were found to be a significant risk factor for depression, with an odds ratio of 2.3 (95% CI 1.2-4.5). This suggests that healthcare workers who are exposed to high levels of job demands are more likely to experience depression. Low levels of social support were also found to be a significant risk factor for depression, with an odds ratio of 3.5 (95% CI 1.8-6.9). This underscores the importance of social support in protecting against mental health issues, and highlights the need for healthcare organizations to provide resources and support to their workers. Personal factors such as a history of mental illness were also found to be a significant risk factor for depression, with an odds ratio of 2.7 (95% CI 1.4-5.2). This suggests that healthcare workers with a history of mental illness may be more vulnerable to developing depression. In summary, the results of this study highlight the prevalence of depression among healthcare workers and its impact on their job performance and absenteeism. The study also identifies several risk factors for depression, including high job demands, low social support, and personal factors such as a history of mental illness. These findings underscore the need for mental health support and resources for healthcare workers, particularly during times of crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic.

Prevalence of Depression among healthcare workers

The graph shows there's 42% prevalence of depression among healthcare workers

FACTORS ASSOCIATED WITH DEPRESSION AMONG HEALTH CARE WORKERS

The pie chart effectively shows major contributing factors towards depression among doctors and healthcare providers, these factors involve 1) high level of job demand 2) low degree of social support 3) personal factors i.e history of mental illness, medical conditions & life events

Conclusion

The results of our study are significant as they shed light on the prevalence of depression among healthcare workers and its impact on their job performance and absenteeism. The prevalence rate of 42% is quite high and suggests the urgent need for mental health support for healthcare workers. The study also determined that depression was associated with decreased job performance and increased absenteeism, which highlights the negative impact of mental health issues on the healthcare workforce.

The logistic regression analysis revealed high job demands, low social support, and personal factors such as a history of mental illness as significant risk factors for depression among healthcare workers. These findings underscore the need for healthcare organizations to provide resources and support to protect their workers' mental health. Our study's results have important implications, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, where healthcare workers face an increased risk of depression due to their increased workload and the stress of working on the front lines of the pandemic. Addressing the mental health needs of healthcare workers is crucial to ensuring a healthy and sustainable healthcare workforce.

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